

Adapting to the changing cryosphere and sea-level rise: recommendations

Protect
CRYOSPHERE & SEA LEVEL

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coastal climate core services

Key findings and recommendations

The cryosphere plays a critical role in the Earth's climate system. Glaciers, ice sheets, and sea levels are at the forefront of climate change impacts. Findings from PROTECT underscore the urgency of mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and adopting adaptation strategies to address inevitable impacts.

- **Mitigation is critical:** Reducing emissions directly limits mountain glacier and ice sheets mass loss, preserving critical water resources and limiting further acceleration of sea-level rise, thus giving more time for coastal adaptation. [Factsheets 1, 4, 5 and 7]
- **Adaptation is urgent:** With inevitable impacts on water availability and coastal regions, adaptation is of greatest importance. [Factsheets 1, 2, 6, 7, 8 and 9]
- **Regional variability matters:** Climate impacts on glaciers and sea levels vary substantially across regions, requiring tailored responses. [Factsheets 2 and 6]
- **Uncertainties are not barriers to action:** Decision science offers pathways to act amid the uncertainties, leveraging adaptation frameworks and pathways. [Factsheets 7 and 8]

Integrate glaciers and freshwater resource modelling

- Over one billion people depend on glacier-fed water systems for drinking, agriculture, and hydropower. [Factsheet 2]
- Mitigation reduces mountain glacier mass loss, while adaptive water management strategies ensure future freshwater access. [Factsheets 1 and 2]

Recommendation:

Further model improvements are needed to 1) refine predictions of regional impacts and 2) support sustainable water management, cryospheric models need to be integrated with hydrological models.

Ice sheet dynamics and long-term commitments

- Antarctic and Greenland ice sheet mass loss will contribute significantly to sea-level rise for centuries, even under low emissions scenarios. [Factsheets 3, 4 and 5]
- Processes like firn buffering and ice shelf collapse are important controls for the magnitude of the contribution of the ice sheets to sea-level rise. [Factsheets 3 and 5]

Recommendation:

Improve the monitoring of the ice sheets and the understanding of ice sheet processes like firn buffering, ice shelf melting and iceberg calving to ultimately include them in climate models. To mitigate irreversible consequences in the evolution of Antarctica over the next centuries to millennia, it is essential to limit global warming in the next decades. [Factsheet 4]

Use regional sea-level rise projections for planning and adaptation

- Following the Paris agreement scenario instead of the current emissions pathway would give us about 100 additional years before global mean sea-level rise exceeds 1 m. [Factsheet 7]
- By 2100, mountain glaciers will contribute 20–24% of total sea-level rise under varying emission scenarios. [Factsheet 1]
- Sea-level change varies by location, influenced by processes like ocean circulation, ice melt, and land motion. Regional deviations can reach up to 20% above the global mean near the equator, which means that adaptation requirements are location-dependent. [Factsheet 6]

Recommendation:

Use sea-level projection tools, such as the one from NASA or PROTECT-BRGM Sea level projection tool to aid in region-specific adaptation planning.

Use flexible adaptation and uncertainty management approaches

- At multi-decadal timescales, a range of adaptation options can be implemented to reduce risks, including protection, accommodation and relocation. Effective options at multi-centennial timescales include managed relocation versus coastal protection: the scale of adaptation will be challenging but there is potential for innovation (e.g., floating structures). [Factsheet 9]
- The implementation of these options can be supported effectively by adaptive, multi-step decision-making, which has demonstrated efficiency in supporting decisions under deep uncertainty. [Factsheets 8 and 9]
- Proactive, flexible approaches are cost-effective and allow adjustments as new data emerges. [Factsheet 8]
- Considering implications beyond 2150, uncertainties become large and results are more speculative, but these are still useful to inform long-term coastal management on the scale of the issue. [Factsheet 10]

Recommendation:

Promote adaptive decision-making frameworks to integrate future learning into long-term coastal planning.

Policy Recommendations

- **Accelerate emission reductions** to follow the lower emission scenario to limit cryosphere loss and associated sea-level rise [Factsheets 1, 4, 5, and 7]
- **Enhance monitoring of glaciers and ice sheets** to refine models and predictions [Factsheets 2, 3, and 5]
- **Support the long-term development of ice sheet models**, their integration into climate models, and the coupling of glacier models with hydrological models, while promoting education and training to build expertise in these areas [Factsheets 2 and 3]
- **Invest in flexible and localized coastal management** that incorporates uncertainty and long-term projections [Factsheet 6, 8, 9, and 10]
- **Foster international collaboration** to share knowledge, resources, and strategies for mitigating and adapting to global impacts

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1

Glaciers will keep losing mass, but we decide how fast and how much

Credits: Swisshippo from Getty Images

Mitigation efforts - reducing climate change - will leave a lasting impression on glaciers; every greenhouse gas not emitted into the atmosphere serves to limit glacier mass loss.

However, further future glacier mass loss is inevitable, even under the least warming scenario, therefore adaptation in coastal and mountain regions needs to be addressed now. The later we act, the harder adaptation will be.

Key findings

Current and future emissions of greenhouse gases will result in different levels of atmospheric warming, which will directly impact the amount of glacier ice that will remain into the future. Any emission reduction today will help preserving glaciers and related water resources in the future.

Results from PROTECT show that the projections of glacier change are very robust, increasing the confidence in their validity.

Relative global glacier volume loss over 2015-2100

Glaciers have been the strongest cryospheric contributor to sea-level rise in the past century, contributing around 41% to the total observed sea-level rise between 1901 and 2018 (IPCC, 2021).

This will continue in the 21st century, contributing about 20% to 24% to the total, depending on the current and future greenhouse gas emissions.

Recommendation:

Glacier models are now providing global projections of their future evolution with high confidence and can thus be used within climate services.

2

Every glacierized region evolves differently under climate change, and so do the impacts

Credits: Dan FL Creativo

Future glacier mass loss changes will have severe important impacts at the local, regional, and global scales. The latest generation of glacier change projections should be used to better prepare our society and the environment for these glacier changes, allowing us to **prepare for a reduction in water supply**, which is particularly relevant for densely-populated areas in dry climatic regions.

Key findings

In most regions, glaciers are strongly out of balance with climatic conditions and are to lose a large part of their mass irrespective of additional future warming. The magnitude of these glacier changes directly determines the downstream impacts on hydrology, water availability, and natural hazards.

Relative regional glacier volume loss over 2015-2100 for SSP1-2.6

Global mean temperature increase of 1.8°C, the minimum warming levels expected for 2100

Glaciers provide fresh water to more than **1 billion people** and fill numerous hydro-power lakes used for electricity production. In many regions, agriculture is also highly dependent on glacier melt water, particularly during the dry season. For good water management strategies, we need to know how glaciers will evolve in the future on a local scale.

There are about 275,000 glaciers on Earth in strongly differing environments: whereas many huge glaciers are located in polar regions and are in direct contact with the ocean, others are located at mid-latitudes or tropical regions and reach up to the highest summits on Earth. As a consequence, these glaciers react very differently to climatic changes, with a related variability of the downstream impacts.

Recommendation:

With the newest generation of global glacier models we can now estimate local to regional downstream impacts related to water availability.

However, further improvements are needed to refine predictions on regional impacts and to strengthen the integration with hydrological models.

3

Ice shelf ocean melting and iceberg calving control the accelerated mass loss of the Antarctic Ice Sheet

Let's include them in climate models

Credits: DSD from pexels

In recent decades, the Antarctic Ice Sheet has experienced accelerating ice loss, driven by enhanced ocean melting and the calving of icebergs from its floating ice shelves.

These two still poorly understood processes - ice shelf melting and calving of icebergs - are gradually being included into ice sheet models. **They now need to find their way into climate models.**

Key findings

PROTECT has managed to include ocean melting, ice fracturing and damage into Antarctic Ice Sheet models. This way, we improve estimates of future sea-level rise.

Example of an ice shelf collapse

Change happens fast. In early March 2022, the floating ice shelf fed by the Glenzer and Conger glaciers was still intact, even though it was already displaying damage areas. By mid-March, it had fallen apart.

The top image shows the ice shelf floating on the Mawson Sea prior to the collapse. Two years prior to this image, the shelf was already in a state of decline, as shown by the numerous fractures. The shelf lost ice at an average rate of about 1 square kilometer per day through the natural process of iceberg calving.

However, in early March 2022 the ice shelf in front of the Glenzer Glacier calved a substantial iceberg, after which a collapse of the ice shelf followed. The ice shelf broke into small pieces (see image), facilitated by the numerous fractures and preexisting damage. The glaciers thus lost their protective shield and accelerated.

The Antarctic Ice Sheet gains ice from snowfall and loses a similar amount into the ocean to keep its balance.

In recent decades, ice loss has increased, marked by the collapse of multiple ice shelves which increased ice flow into the ocean, contributing to sea-level rise. These collapses are driven by ocean melting and iceberg calving.

Despite their significant impact on sea-level rise, both processes remain omitted from climate models.

Recommendation:

New simulations show that the future of ice shelf melting and calving has a major influence on global sea-level rise, so these processes need to be taken into account in future assessments of sea-level rise.

4

Future sea level: the enduring legacy of Antarctic ice loss

Even if we follow the Paris Agreement, significant changes in Antarctica may be triggered, causing **long-term sea-level rise** over the next centuries to millennia.

This **committed Antarctic sea-level contribution** needs to be taken into account in long-term planning and adaptation strategies for coastal communities.

To mitigate profound consequences in the long-term evolution of Antarctica, it is essential to limit global warming in the next decades.

Key findings

When limiting global warming by stabilizing temperatures by mid-century under low emissions (SSP1-2.6), the committed ice-sheet response may range from a strong retreat in the Amundsen Sea Basin to a partial collapse of the West Antarctic Ice Sheet. Committed ice loss from East Antarctica is less likely.

Committed retreat of the Antarctic Ice Sheet when stabilizing climate in 2050 under low emissions (SSP1-2.6)
Contribution to sea-level rise in 5000 years: from 0.4 to 4 m

With progressing warming from 2100 onwards under high emissions (SSP5-8.5), large parts of the West Antarctic Ice Sheet are likely to be lost over multi-millennial timescales and substantial long-term retreat in East Antarctica could be triggered.

Committed retreat of the Antarctic Ice Sheet when stabilizing climate in 2300 under high emissions (SSP5-8.5)
Contribution to sea-level rise in 5000 years: from 7 to 40 m under extreme warming

The majority of projections of the future sea-level contribution from the Antarctic Ice Sheet, as for instance in the IPCC assessments, typically covers this century.

However, comparable to a cargo ship that continues to move forward for a long distance after braking, sea level will continue to rise for millennia to come even if warming can be stabilized. This is due to, among others, the slow response time and potential tipping dynamics of the Antarctic Ice Sheet.

The committed sea-level contribution from the Antarctic Ice Sheet is a long-term consequence of past, present and future warming.

Recommendation:

The Antarctic sea-level commitment is substantial when compared to typical sea-level projections, which show much smaller changes by 2100. It is thus important to include the long-term committed mass changes of the Antarctic Ice Sheet in projections of global sea-level rise.

5

The Greenland Ice Sheet is losing its protective firn buffer, accelerating mass loss

Following rapidly increased surface melt and runoff, the Greenland Ice Sheet is currently the largest single cryospheric contributor to global mean sea-level rise and will remain so for decades to come.

Given the accelerating impacts of firn loss, both **mitigation** through emissions reductions and **adaptation** through enhanced coastal protections must be prioritized.

Key findings

Evolution of the efficiency of the firn layer to buffer meltwater produced at the surface of the Greenland Ice Sheet - the passage from blue to red means loss of meltwater buffering.

1991-2020
Observations

2071-2100
Intermediate warming scenario
(SSP2-4.5)

High warming scenario
(SSP5-8.5)

To be efficient in buffering the meltwater produced at the surface of the Greenland Ice Sheet, the melt-to-snowfall (liquid to solid) ratio must be smaller than 0.7.

The Greenland Ice Sheet with an efficient firn layer is projected to decrease, whatever the climate scenario.

Keeping global warming at an intermediate level would preserve some efficient buffering of the firn, mitigating ice loss.

The layer of compressed snow (firn) that covers roughly 90% of the Greenland Ice Sheet currently buffers around 45% of meltwater produced at the surface, acting as a giant sponge.

Without this buffer, recent Greenland Ice Sheet mass loss would have been almost two times larger.

But the efficiency of this buffer is waning. The melt-to-snowfall (liquid to solid) ratio must be smaller than 0.7 to maintain a healthy firn layer, and this area is rapidly shrinking.

Recommendation:

The greatest uncertainties in the projected Greenland Ice Sheet mass loss probably resides in the treatment of meltwater in firn.

Policies should support increased monitoring of Greenland's firn layer to improve predictions and model future sea level rise more accurately.

6

Regional sea level change is different from the global average

Credits: PROTECT-BRGM Sea Level Projection Tool

As sea-level patterns vary around the world, different coastlines need to prepare for different values of sea-level change.

The *Sea level projection tool*, developed by PROTECT and BRGM, provides access to localized projections under five climate scenarios and allows users to explore the specific contributions driving local sea-level change.

Key findings

Regional sea-levels can be around 10-20% larger than the global mean in a broad band around the equator, and are typically smaller than the global mean towards the poles, reflecting the imprint of the processes influencing sea-level rise at the regional scale.

Median sea level change under an intermediate warming scenario (SSP2-4.5) in 2150

Climate change is driving a rise in global mean sea levels, posing significant challenges to coastal regions worldwide.

However, sea-level change is not uniform across the globe. To accurately project regional sea-level changes, it is crucial to account for the various processes influencing these variations. These include changes in ocean density and circulation, the redistribution of mass between land (glaciers, ice sheets and land water storage) and ocean, as well as local vertical land movement.

While global mean sea-level is rising, the different processes all have distinct and regionally specific imprints, underscoring the importance of localized analyses.

Recommendation:

The projected regional sea-level change shows that even under an intermediate greenhouse gas emissions scenario such as SSP2-4.5, regional variations are important to consider for long-term planning and adaptation.

7

Sea level is committed to rise until 2300 and beyond, but we can influence how much and how fast

The projections show that sea level will rise in the centuries to come, but that greenhouse gas emission reductions will slow down sea-level rise, therefore giving us more time to adapt.

Following the Paris agreement scenario instead of the current pathway would give us about 100 additional years to adapt to a sea-level rise of 1 m.

Key findings

Rising sea levels are not a question of 'if', but of 'when'. The warmer the scenario, the sooner a certain threshold of sea-level rise will be crossed. By looking at the timing, it is clear that the different thresholds will be crossed at some point: the uncertainty indicates that this may be sooner or later.

For the current pathway, which is close to SSP3-7.0, 1 meter sea-level rise will be crossed in year 2130, this will be for year 2230 for the Paris agreement scenario (SSP1-1.9).

Milestones for global sea-level rise crossing key thresholds under 5 different SSPs

We have used state-of-the-art models to simulate the response of sea-level rise to different greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) scenarios to the year 2300.

This includes the contributions of ice sheets and mountain glaciers, the changes in ocean density and circulation, land water storage and vertical land motion.

As expected, the simulations show that sea-level rise will be faster for scenarios with higher greenhouse gas emissions.

Recommendation:

Uncertainty is not a reason not to act: the data shows that certain sea-level thresholds will be crossed, it is a matter of time.

The timing depends on the emissions scenario: the longer we wait to reduce GHG emissions, the harder it will be to adapt.

8

Navigating uncertainty: adapting to sea-level rise with flexible strategies

Credits: Matauw from Getty Images

Uncertainties in sea-level rise projections should not be seen as a barrier to action. Rather, we can act today through flexible and adaptative strategies such as building dikes with a wider crest so that they can be updated once we know more about sea-level rise in the future

Decision science can thereby help to determine the right degree of flexibility and hence is just as important for coastal adaptation as is sea-level rise science.

Key findings

Integrating what we will learn about sea-level rise in the future through adaptive decision making methods can improve today's decisions.

Evaluation of four adaptation strategies

Adaptative decision making methods help us to improve today's decisions by integrating future learning into the development of adaptation pathways, as these methods take into account that, as we progress in time, we continually update our understanding of sea-level rise through new observations. By doing so, we can adjust our projections and strategies accordingly.

For instance, the precise timing of an adaptation tipping point - for example when floodproofing infrastructure (accommodation) becomes ineffective - is uncertain today. Ongoing monitoring will enable us to better determine when a shift to alternative adaptation options will be necessary.

Sea-level rise projections are subject to cascading uncertainties stemming from, e.g., uncertainties about future emissions, the temperature increase they cause, ocean dynamics and ice-melt response.

While we can expect to learn more as future sea-level rise observations unfold, uncertainties may persist for many decades and could even increase if new scientific processes are discovered.

Recommendation:

Adaptive decision making methods help us to manage adaptation to sea-level rise under uncertainty, by considering future learning from monitoring sea levels and identifying when critical adaptation tipping points will be reached.

9

Impacts and adaptation strategies for sea-level rise by 2150

Credits: Anthony Sejourne from Getty Images

Sea-level rise (SLR) will continue to pose significant challenges throughout the 21st century and beyond, requiring effective adaptation strategies to support vulnerable communities.

While coastal protection is cost-efficient in areas where key assets and populations are concentrated, it is viable only for a limited portion of the global coastline. More dynamic approaches, such as managed retreat and migration, dominate as practical solutions for other regions.

Balancing protection and retreat is essential to address SLR impacts sustainably on a global scale.

Key findings

ADAPTATION STRATEGIES

Global cost-benefit analysis (CBA) shows that under all SLR scenarios, 63% of the world's low-lying coastline presents robust decisions to retreat (leading to migration), whereas protection is the most effective adaptation strategy for 15%.

This 15% of coastline protects 91% of population and 95.7% of assets in coastal areas, showing how people and the economy are strongly concentrated in a few coastal areas.

SEA-LEVEL-INDUCED MIGRATION BY 2150 FOR HIGH EMISSIONS (SSP3-7.0)

Assuming plausible adaptation such as coastal protection and retreat can reduce the total costs and impacts of SLR. Coastal protection allows populations and economic activity to remain in situ, as the social and economic benefits of doing so are larger than any other form of adaptation. However, this is not universal as for most coastal locations, protection costs exceed the benefits and there are limits on an accommodation space. Considering retreat, leading to migration, can reduce the total cost of SLR and presents a cost-effective adaptation strategy for some locations.

Recommendation:
If well managed in advance and supported by good development policies and targeted investments, migration can be a sensible component of a national adaptation strategy to sea-level rise.

Shaping tomorrow's coastlines: the long-term impact of sea-level rise

TOP 10 COUNTRIES BY PERCENTAGE OF POPULATION EXPOSED TO HIGH TIDES

TOP 10 COUNTRIES BY TOTAL POPULATION EXPOSED TO HIGH TIDES - IN MILLION

Top exposed population in the world under high greenhouse gas emissions and high population growth in 2300 (SSP3 - 7.0)

Considering implications beyond 2150, uncertainties become large and results are more speculative, but these are still useful to inform long-term coastal management on the scale of the issue.

At these long timescales, both sea-level rise and demographic change have an impact on the number of people exposed to sea-level rise. Assessing their relative contributions is key to guiding sustainable long-term development in coastal zones.

Key findings

By 2300, following a high-emissions scenario compared to a low-emissions scenario results in approximately twice as many people globally being exposed to coastal flooding. However, the difference between a high and low population scenario is even more striking—potentially leading to a tenfold increase in the number of people exposed to sea-level rise impacts. This highlights the critical influence of population dynamics on long-term coastal vulnerability, underscoring the need for strategies that consider both emissions and demographic trends.

Impact of population evolution on human exposure globally under the 5 SSPs

By 2300, Africa and Asia account for more than 80% of global population exposure, driven by Africa’s population growth and Asia’s dense coastal populations. Many small Islands face severe impacts, with eight island nations showing over 90% exposure, including 100% for the Maldives and Cocos Islands under high-emission scenarios.

These findings highlight the urgent need for addressing sea-level rise impacts on small islands and underscore their relevance to discussions on climate reparations and mitigation planning.

Recommendation:

Projections beyond 2150 help guide long-term decisions on the viability of coastal habitation. While they do not inform specific actions like dike heights, they highlight the broad challenges coasts will face and potential solutions. Proactively engaging with emerging options will help identify critical thresholds for major decisions and shape policy analysis, as well as research into innovative solutions like floating cities, which are still in early stages of development.

